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The quest for adventure: A Tourist's perspective on choosing attractions in Zambales, Philippines

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine visitors' perceptions regarding factors in selecting attractions in Zambales. A survey questionnaire was conducted with 120 respondents who visited Zambales' man-made or natural attractions to gather data on their profiles and the factors they consider when selecting attractions. The study analyzed factors such as safety and security, management, cleanliness and sanitation, and ambiance/environment. Additionally, the study investigated whether there was a significant difference in the factors considered in selecting attractions based on respondents' profile variables, including gender, age, civil status, occupation, and monthly income. The descriptive research design was used to describe the problems identified, and data were analyzed using percentages and weighted mean. The research was anchored on the Theory of Travel Decision-Making to examine how tourists perceive their needs and how potential destinations, accommodations, or transport systems can fulfill these needs. The results revealed that respondents' profile variables had a significant impact on the factors they consider when selecting attractions. The study's findings could help attraction managers improve their services and amenities, making them more attractive to visitors. Overall, this study provided valuable insights into understanding the factors that affect visitors' attraction selection in Zambales.

Keywords: Attractions; Hospitality; Perception; Tourist; Travel decision-making; Zambales.

1 Introduction

Tourism is more frequently referred to as the world's biggest and fastest-growing industry. Together with this trend, the importance of visitor perception has been increasingly analyzed and is considered a significant factor in destination attractiveness. An investigation of the impact of destination attributes on the frequency of visitors and their intention to return could demonstrate the strengths and weaknesses of a destination by assessing its attractiveness level. The visitor's information and knowledge about the destination can assist with development and planning, and marketing, and can also improve the management of a destination. In other words, the more impressed visitors are with the destination, the greater visitation frequency is expected. Tourist attractions, as a set of features or attributes where some features are 'given' and others are partly 'man-made'. 'Given' or natural attributes include a number of natural features of tourism destinations – like the climate, scenery, beaches, mountains, and historical and cultural buildings. The 'man-made' features include accommodation and transportation, package tours, sports and recreational facilities – all of which can be tailored to visitor preferences, depending on budget restrictions. Thus, for the purpose of this study a tourist destination is seen as a place away from the tourists' home, and includes the perception a tourist has of the destination's attractions [1].

In addition, tourism is a social, cultural, and economic which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purposes. These people are called visitors. A

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visitor is a traveler taking a trip to a main destination outside his/her usual environment, for less than a year, for any main purpose (business, leisure or other personal purpose) other than to be employed by a resident entity in the country or place visited. A visitor (domestic, inbound or outbound) is classified as a tourist (or overnight visitor), if his/her trip includes an overnight stay, or as a same-day visitor (or excursionist), if his/her trip does not include an overnight stay. Tourism is the all-encompassing umbrella term for the activities and industry that create the tourist experience, the defines travel as the activity of moving between different locations often for any purpose but more so for leisure and recreation [2].

Visitors' perspective when selecting a particular attraction are depending to several factors to consider: Safety and Security, Management, Cleanliness and Sanitation, and Ambiance and Environment. Also, the factors to be considered in selecting Attraction when grouped according to their profiles. These factors are vital for the satisfaction to the overall experience of the trip. The ultimate primary purpose of attractions is to attract the customer's attention so that they can come to a specific location and explore the various attractions on vacation. In the travel and tourism industry, attractions therefore play a particularly important role as this attracts visitors from all over the world. Nestled in the Central Luzon region in the Philippines, you can choose from several types of attractions in the second district of Zambales whether it is natural or man-made attractions with considering the factors that is suitable for the visitor's selection.

Early works on attractions affirmed that without attractions, there are no tourists or tourism. The converse is also true as 'tourism attractions' exist because of tourists and they are 'produced' and marketed as such due to the availability of tourists. Tourists visit a destination because there is a tourist attraction which definitely has an image. However, from an ontological point of view, Gunn's sweeping statement does not take into consideration excursionists or domestic visitors who can visit the attractions without necessarily sleeping over in that area. He assumes that only tourists (overnight spenders) consume attractions [3].

The first component of the tourism system is the demand side, namely the consumers of tourism represented by tourists. Similarly, to the definition of tourism, the literature review reveals it is difficult to find agreement on the definition of tourists. Consequently, based on the Glossary of Tourism Terms [2], this thesis defines tourist as someone who moves from their usual place of residence to a different place for leisure, study or work purposes for a short-term period between a couple of days to one year maximum. As mentioned in the introductory chapter, just as tourism has evolved, so has the perception of tourists from the researchers' point of view. Contemporary tourists are no longer considered just consumers of the tourism products, but are seen as producers of experiences. Nowadays, tourism is more about feelings than consumption in a materialistic way. The researches at home and abroad for evaluating tourism destination mainly involve the analysis of tourist environment carrying capacity, the evaluation regarding tourist horizon of tourism destination, tourism resources development and the overall planning related to impact on ecological environmental impact, environmental quality and sustainable development system of the tourism destination. Through the process of reviewing the related literature, the discussion indicates that the research of tourism destinations has obtained many achievements and laid a certain foundation for later studies, however, it still has some demerits. The application of tourism destination evaluation method and model has mostly confined to the traditional static and linear evaluation method, and the aspects of tourist economy and society are not mentioned enough. Safety and security are important to tourists. In fact, research finds that safety and security are the most important travel considerations for some tourists [4]. Safety refers to protection of customers and employees from potential injury or death. Security is guarding against loss of life, belongings, and property. According to the (US) National Crime Prevention Institute 2014, research can categorize safety and security measures using physical devices and involving employees' behavioural procedures.

Even though a large number of core elements encourage people to visit destinations, mental and physical health relaxation possesses a dominant position amongst all. Experiencing a cleanliness, hygienic environment while traveling, makes individuals more satisfied and no immediate alternatives can replace this need. Despite the importance of sanitation and hand hygiene safety during tour time, concepts are not developing to review the guard against hygiene-related illness some of which may be fatal while others can lead to expensive medical care. The goal of this paper is to provide guidance on applications to prevent any adverse consequences for the travellers coming to Bangladesh.

As measured by economic expenditure, the largest nature-based subsectors are those that include extensive accommodation and activity infrastructure as well as associated amenity migration and residential property development. In these cases, the natural environment is used principally as an outdoor playground. The main examples are the ski industry, the marina industry, and the beach tourism sector. In research terms, these are considered as mass or mainstream tourism. Ski resorts rely on retail shopping precincts and residential land sales as well as on lift ticket sales, but their position and layout are dictated by terrain and climate, and many are on public land originally allocated for forestry or conservation. In developed nations, beach and marina tourism are largely integrated into coastal cities.

Developing nations typically follow the enclave resort model, which may eventually develop into resort towns. While privately-owned tourism enterprises are common, there are instances where government agencies directly own them. Alternatively, they may be privately owned by government officials through patronage systems. Outdoor tourism activities, which involve many participants, typically require less infrastructure and expenditure. These activities are often available as independent self-supported recreation or commercial tourism products. Additionally, in developing nations, Human Resource Management plays a vital role in improving organizational performance and contributes to the success of businesses [21].

Environment tourism uses outdoor natural environments as a setting for excitement-based recreation rather than appreciation of nature. There is, however, considerable overlap both in individual motivations and in the design of commercial products, which often include nature-based, adventurous, and cultural components in a single product. Watching wildlife can be exciting as well as educational, and many adventure activities take place in spectacular landscapes. At least 45 different outdoor activities are offered as adventure tourism products. Risk management and participant motivations for these have been examined in particular detail.

This study holds immense significance in the tourism industry of Zambales. By analysing the factors that visitors consider while selecting attractions, it will provide crucial information and knowledge that can benefit various stakeholders. Firstly, the findings of this study will be valuable to the tourism administrators. They will be able to use this research to develop and enhance the visitor facilities of an attraction. By gaining a better understanding of their visitors and the local tourism market, tourism businesses can improve their services and attract more visitors to the area. Secondly, the study will be beneficial to the business owners who run the attractions. They will be able to determine how they can accommodate and adjust to the needs of visitors. By using the data acquired from this research, they can identify any issues that may exist and develop better strategies and initiatives aimed at improving their operations. Lastly, this research will serve as a foundation for future researchers. The concepts and findings of this study can be used as a starting point for new research or to assess the validity of existing related studies. It will also provide a cross-reference for them, providing a backdrop or summary of the criteria to consider while choosing Zambales attractions. General, this research will play a crucial role in the tourism industry of Zambales. It will provide valuable insights and knowledge that can be used to develop and enhance the attractions in the area, making it more attractive to visitors and ultimately boosting the local economy.

The study aims to determine the perception of visitors regarding the factors in selecting attractions in Zambales. The research will seek to answer questions about the respondents' profiles in terms of gender, age, status, occupation, monthly income, and preferred type of attraction. It will also investigate the factors in selecting an attraction, such as safety and security, management, cleanliness and sanitation, and ambiance/environment. Additionally, the study will analyse whether there is a significant difference in the factors considered in selecting attractions based on respondents' profile variables.

The study's scope is limited to the visitors' perspective in selecting attractions in Zambales. The researchers will use a survey questionnaire with 120 respondents who have visited Zambales' man-made or natural attractions. The questionnaire will gather data on the respondents' profiles and the factors they consider in selecting attractions. The study will use the descriptive research design to describe the problems identified. The researchers will maintain research ethics by keeping the respondents' names, personal data, and responses confidential. Data will be analysed using percentage and weighted mean.

This study will be anchored on the Theory of Travel Decision-Making [22]. Travel decision-making helps to explain tourists' travel behaviour as the outcome of a cognitive decision-making process which is itself influenced by their perceptions of the environment, their individual characteristics or personality traits as well as the context in which the decision takes place. To capture all aspects, there is a combination of consumer behaviour methods to study individual decision-making processes. Research on travel decision-making often focuses on specific influencing factors or contextual layers individually. Studies that integrate multiple factors, including destination attributes that influence travel behaviour, and consider travel decision-making as a multi-step perceptive process [13]. Tourism is a complex system of several interrelated contextual layers. First, travel behaviour is embedded in the individual attributes of a person [15]. Second, travel behaviour depends on the social context as travel decision-making is influenced by information from the social environment [7]. Third, travel behaviour can be explained by the spatial context [11], as the residential environment (urban/rural, access to airport) and economic or social regional disparities also influence this [6]. A specific feature of travel decisions, in particular destination choices, is that they are negotiation processes between tourists' needs and the destination offer [5]. When applying a behavioural geography perspective to examine travel decision-making, we need to consider how tourists perceive their own needs and how a potential destination, accommodation or transport system can fulfil these needs [13]. The theory is found to be appropriate because of their

essential feature which will be related to factors to consider in selecting attractions in Zambales. Figure 1 illustrates the paradigm of the study which provides the basis for the significant scope of this study. This study will be conducted to know the perception of visitors in selecting attractions in Zambales.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Research Design

The present study utilizes quantitative methodology. This study will be using descriptive survey method. Descriptive research can be explained as a statement of affairs as they are at present with the researcher having no control over variables moreover, descriptive research may be characterized as simply the attempt to determine, describe or identify what is, while analytical research attempts to establish why it is that way or how it came to be. Descriptive research is scientific research that describes events, phenomena or facts systematically dealing with a certain area or population. Descriptive research is aimed at casting light on current issues or problems through a process of data collection that enables them to describe the situation more completely than was possible without employing this method. Descriptive research is also known as statistical research that describes data and characteristics about what practices, level of effectiveness and recovery and processing it answers the question who, what, where, and how, this kind of research also deals with the present existing condition and data gathering. It aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. In its essence, descriptive studies are used to describe various aspects of the phenomenon. In its popular format, descriptive research is used to describe the characteristics and/or behavior of the sample population.

2.2 Respondents and Location

This study will be conducted in Zambales, focusing on one hundred twenty (120) respondents who visited the attractions, whether it is man-made or natural made.

This research used simple random sampling in order for the researcher to gather respondents. Simple random sampling is a subset of individuals chosen from a larger set. Each individual is chosen randomly and entirely by chance and each member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample. Every possible sample of a given size has the same chance of selection.

Figure 1 Map of Zambales, Philippines

2.3 Research Instrument

The study will use a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire made by the researchers will be composed of two (2) parts: Part 1 will cover the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, status, occupation, monthly income, and preferred type of attraction. Part 2 will cover the factors in selecting attractions in terms of the safety and security, management, cleanliness and sanitation, and ambiance /environment. The 4-point Likert scale will be used to get the descriptive interpretation from the respondents, 4- Very Much Considered; 3- Considered; 2- Slightly Considered; and 1-Not Considered. The instrument will be submitted and checked by the Research Professor and Adviser for refinement. Suggestions and comments were taken and incorporated for the improvement of the research instrument. And to test its reliability, Cronbach Alpha was employed.

Table 1 Cronbach Alpha Summary of the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors to be considered in selecting Attraction.

Parameters	Cronbach's Alpha based on Standardized Items	Interpretation (Extent of Reliability)
Safety and Security	0.799	Acceptable
Management	0.761	Acceptable
Cleanliness and Sanitation	0.953	Excellent
Ambiance and Environment	0.902	Excellent

Cronbach Alpha Summary of the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors to be considered in selecting Attraction. Based on the result, the Assessment of the respondents' perception on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security ($\alpha=0.799$), and Management ($\alpha=0.761$) were "Acceptable". While on the Cleanliness and Sanitation ($\alpha=0.953$), and Ambiance and Environment ($\alpha=0.902$) were "Excellent". Thus, it is indicative that all questions can provide the necessary information to answer the objectives of the study.

The researchers will first seek permission and endorsement from the LGU Tourism Office before administering the survey questionnaire to the visitors as respondents. They will explain the study's objectives and instructions for answering all items to the respondents. After a week, the questionnaires will be collected for data tabulation, analysis, and interpretation.

To analyze the collected data, the researchers will use descriptive statistical tools such as frequency to count the occurrence of variables, percentage to obtain the profile of respondents and the factors in selecting attractions in Zambales, and weighted mean to calculate the average on the factors to be considered in selecting attractions. The researchers will also use analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the significance of differences in the mean of variables. The software SPSS will be utilized to compute ANOVA. The researchers will use ANOVA to test the hypotheses regarding H_0 , which is whether there is a significant difference in the factors in selecting an attraction when grouped according to profile variables.

The researchers will use the SPSS Statistical for Psychological Software System to determine the significance of the data. If the computed P value is greater than ($>$) 0.05, the null hypothesis will be accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference. Conversely, if the computed P value is less than ($<$) 0.05, the alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis will be rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Profile of the Respondents

Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents,, the majority 63 or equivalent to 38.30% were females, 46 or equivalent to 38.30% were males and 11 or equivalent to 9.20% were LGBTQ+. This means that majority of the respondents who fond to travel were females. According to [9], women are statistically and actually much more likely love to travel than men. Indeed, women's dominance of travel is both startling and decisive. In addition, in the U.S., women dominate leisure travel by a 63% to 37% ratio over men. Worldwide there is a similar skew, with 64% of global travellers being female, versus 36% male [20].

Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents, the majority were from the age group of 18 to 25 years old which was 49 or equivalent to 40.80%; 36 or equivalent to 30.00% were from the age group of 26 to 33 years old; 15 or equivalent of 12.50% were from the age group of 34 to 41 years old; and 10 or equivalent of 8.30% were from the age group of 42 to 49 years old, and 50 years old and above. The mean age was 31 years old. This revealed that respondents who travel more were between the ages of 18 and 25 and the most dominant in the survey which belongs to millennials, and they are likely seeking out new knowledge and experiences.

Civil Status. Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents, the majority 78 or equivalent of 65.00% were single, 33 or equivalent to 27.50% were married, 5 or equivalent to 4.20 were widows, and 4 or equivalent of 3.30% were others. This implies that the respondents were single who can go into different places to explore new things. According to [8], Now that Covid has finally been controlled and more countries are feeling the impetus to reopen for tourism, international travel is back with a vengeance. Passenger numbers for 2022 already (far) exceed the last two years, and amid the surge, some pretty interesting travel trends are emerging: the growing fascination with solo or single traveller is one of them. Single are the one who love to explore new places with new experience.

Occupation. Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents, the majority 69 or equivalent of 57.50% were from others (different occupations), 23 or equivalent to 19.20% were government employees, 15 or equivalent to 12.50 were private employees, and 13 or equivalent of 10.80% were entrepreneurs. The data clearly demonstrate that the respondents were from different field/occupation which they can manage their time to go into different places to explore new things. According to [16], whatever job/occupation you have travel is integral to a lifelong-learning process, travel introduces you to new perspectives, travel reconnects us with our life and make our jobs meaningful.

Monthly Income. Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents, the majority 42 or equivalent of 35.00% were 5,000 below; 21 or equivalent of 17.50% were 5,001 to 10,000; 17 or equivalent to 14.20% were 10,001 to 15,000 and 20,001 to 25,000; 12 or equivalent to 10.00% were 15,001 to 20,000; 6 or equivalent to 5.00% were 30,001 and above; and 5 or equivalent of 4.20% were 25,001 to 30,000. The mean monthly income was 12,417.09. This means that the respondents' monthly income was categorized as poor but tried to expose themselves to the attractions/destinations to have new experiences for as long as it is not expensive. According to [14] suggested eight (8) top tips on how you can travel the world for cheap. Pick the right destination to make the best with your budget, do your research to find the lowest airfare, curb your meals expenses by cooking in your trip, live it up with some free events, pack light with a minimalist packing list, do volunteer work exchange with World packers, seek out the discounts to travel cheaper, and use your skills to make money travelling

Preferred Type of Attraction. Out of the one hundred twenty (120) respondents, the majority of 97 or equivalent to 80.80% preferred natural-made and 23 or equivalent of 19.20% preferred man-made. This indicates that most of the respondents love natural made attractions. According to [10], young people or now already known as millennials would prefer to spend money to travel and visit nature tourism because of their insufficient exposure to nature. They are starting to engage to natural environment since they were unable to do so when they were still young due to being exposed to digital technology. More and more attractions are utilizing natural environment to assure that the young travellers will be able to enjoy the nature such as beaches and equestrian.

3.2 Factors in selecting Attraction

Table 2 shows the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security. The respondents assessed "Very Much Considered" Harmful animals are not visible in the area with a weighted mean of 3.77 and ranked 1, Clarity of the signs and directives that care for the safety and health of the visitors with a weighted mean of 3.75 and ranked 2, Availability of assistance local guides with a weighted mean of 3.67 and ranked 3, Orderly and easily accessible rescue equipment near the area with a weighted mean of 3.64 and ranked 4 and Reminders are given by the management to protect the property and belongings of customers with a weighted mean of 3.61 and ranked 5. The computed overall weighted mean on the Perception of the Respondents on the in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security was 3.69 with a qualitative interpretation of "Very Much Considered". This implies that the safety and security of the guests/tourists should be prioritized in all aspects. The safety and security are the most important travel considerations for some tourists [23]. Also, the protection of customers from any loss of life, belongings, and property [4].

Table 2 Safety and Security.

	Safety and Security	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	Orderly and easily accessible rescue equipment near the area.	3.64	Very Much Considered	4
2	Reminders are given by the management to protect the property and belongings of customers.	3.61	Very Much Considered	5
3	Clarity of the signs and directives that care for the safety and health of the visitors.	3.75	Very Much Considered	2
4	Availability of assistance from local guides.	3.67	Very Much Considered	3
5	Harmful animals are not visible in the area.	3.77	Very Much Considered	1
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.69	Very Much Considered	

Table 3 Management

	Management	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	There is a control on the number of visitors to protect the area.	3.73	Very Much Considered	4
2	The local people/ employee are friendly towards visitors.	3.72	Very Much Considered	5
3	The quality of service is provided.	3.77	Very Much Considered	1
4	The price for food and other service fee is reasonable.	3.74	Very Much Considered	2.5
5	The professionalism of the people / employee.	3.74	Very Much Considered	2.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.74	Very Much Considered	

Table 3 shows the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security. The respondents assessed “Very Much Considered” The quality of service is provided with a weighted mean of 3.77 and ranked 1, The price for food and other service fee is reasonable, and The professionalism of the people/employee with a weighted mean of 3.74 and ranked 2.5, There is a control on the number of visitors to protect the area with a weighted mean of 3.73 and ranked 4 and The local people/ employee are friendly towards visitors with a weighted mean of 3.72 and ranked 5. The computed overall weighted mean on the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Management was 3.74 with a qualitative interpretation of “Very Much Considered”.

Table 4 shows the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation. The respondents assessed “Very Much Considered” Effectiveness of garbage and disposal segregation, and The foods are fresh and safe to eat by the visitors with a weighted mean of 3.87 and ranked 1.5, The foods are clean and well-packed with a weighted mean of 3.86 and ranked 3, The availability of potable/drinking water with a weighted mean of 3.85 and ranked 4 and The attraction is clean and garbage free with a weighted mean of 3.83 and ranked 5. The computed overall weighted mean on the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation was 3.86 with a qualitative interpretation of “Very Much Considered”. This indicates that cleanliness and sanitation are the factors that the guests/tourists are looking into exploring the place. In the study of [12], experiencing cleanliness, hygienic environment most especially the food in the place while traveling, makes individuals more satisfied and no immediate alternatives can replace this need.

Table 4 Cleanliness and Sanitation

	Cleanliness and Sanitation	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	Effectiveness of garbage and disposal segregation	3.87	Very Much Considered	1.5
2	The foods are clean and well-packed.	3.86	Very Much Considered	3
3	The attraction is clean and garbage free.	3.83	Very Much Considered	5
4	The availability of potable/drinking water.	3.85	Very Much Considered	4
5	The foods are fresh and safe to eat by the visitors.	3.87	Very Much Considered	1.5
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.86	Very Much Considered	

Table 5 Ambiance and Environment

	Ambiance and Environment	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	The place is good for relaxation and stress-free surroundings.	3.88	Very Much Considered	1
2	The place offers recreational activities and other activities for single /team use.	3.70	Very Much Considered	5
3	The place is a unique and picture-perfect spot.	3.80	Very Much Considered	2
4	The place promotes authentic food and culture.	3.77	Very Much Considered	4
5	The place is nature friendly or with a nature-friendly environment.	3.79	Very Much Considered	3
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.79	Very Much Considered	

Table 5 shows the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation. The respondents assessed "Very Much Considered" The place is good for relaxation and stress-free surroundings with a weighted mean of 3.88 and ranked 1, The place is a unique and picture-perfect spot with a weighted mean of 3.80 and ranked 2, The place is nature friendly or with a nature-friendly environment with a weighted mean of 3.79 and ranked 3, The place promotes authentic food and culture with a weighted mean of 3.74 and ranked 4, and The place offers recreational activities and other activities for single /team use with a weighted mean of 3.70 and ranked 5. The computed overall weighted mean on the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in selecting Attraction as to Ambiance and Environment was 3.79 with a qualitative interpretation of "Very Much Considered". This implies that the factors that the respondents looking is the place or sport which has unique offerings. In the study of [2], tourists felt relaxed with family members and friends and liked to be with them when facing challenges in an unfamiliar environment. Therefore, this factor was referred to as the kinship/relax factor.

Table 6 shows the summary table of the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors in Selecting Attraction. The respondents assessed all "Very Much Considered" on Cleanliness and Sanitation with a weighted mean of 3.65 and ranked 1; Ambiance and Environment with a weighted mean of 3.79 and ranked 2; Management with a weighted mean of 3.74 and ranked 3; and Safety and Security with a weighted mean of 3.69 and ranked 4. The computed grand weighted mean of the Perception of the Respondents on the Factors to be Considered in Selecting Attraction was 3.77 with a qualitative interpretation of "Very Much Considered". As emphasized by [17] that Linking a destination to the benefits perceived by the tourist will be pointless if such a place cannot offer a high level of public safety, cleanliness, an adequate transport system and adequate signage. With this, the tourist can move around safely, knowing the police are constantly patrolling and seeing the clear signage indicating the different places of interest, in a clean, quiet setting.

Table 6 Selecting Attraction

	Factors to be considered in selecting Attraction	Overall Weighted Mean	Qualitative Interpretation	Rank
1	Safety and Security	3.69	Very Much Considered	4
2	Management	3.74	Very Much Considered	3
3	Cleanliness and Sanitation	3.86	Very Much Considered	1
4	Ambiance and Environment	3.79	Very Much Considered	2
	Grand Mean	3.77	Very Much Considered	

3.3 Test of difference on the factors in selecting Attraction when grouped according to profile variables.

The Analysis of Variance to test difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security when grouped according to profile variables. The computed value of 0.467 for Gender, 0.519 for Age, 0.859 for Civil Status, 0.198 for Occupation, 0.182 for Monthly Income, and 0.179 for Preferred Type of Attraction was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, hence, there is no significant difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Safety and Security when grouped according to profile variables. This implies that the safety and security apply whatever sex, age, civil status, occupation, monthly income, and preferred type of attraction they are located into. Safety and security are important to tourists. In fact, research finds that safety and security are the most important travel considerations for some tourists. In addition, the installation of safety devices and behavioral security measures reduces tourists' anxiety and increases their sense of safety, especially among tourists who have had previous exposure to instances of crime [4].

The Analysis of Variance to test difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Management when grouped according to profile variables. The computed value of 0.972 for Gender, 0.519 for Age, 0.376 for Civil Status, 0.129 for Monthly Income, and 0.080 for Preferred Type of Attraction was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, hence, there is no significant difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Management when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.036 for occupation was lower than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Management. This implies that as to management, occupation is important to consider because as the guests earned degrees their expectations and standards become more higher. In the study of [2] shows that management in tourist destinations would benefit from provision of the authentic travel experience integrated with zoning the travel destination. Furthermore, Measures included management of tourists, employees, organizations, and environment. Administrative officers recognized that crowding must be managed in an integrated procedure; however, they tended to ignore the psychological management perspective. As tourists perceived environments in various ways, it is essential to use different management strategies at different groups.

The Analysis of Variance to test difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation when grouped according to profile variables. The computed value of 0.429 for Gender, 0.618 for Civil Status, 0.709 for Occupation, 0.908 for Monthly Income, and 0.129 for Preferred Type of Attraction was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, hence, there is no significant difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation when grouped according to profile variables. On the other hand, the computed value of 0.009 for age was lower than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence, there is a significant difference on the factors to be considered in selecting Attraction as to Cleanliness and Sanitation. The results show that age is necessary to consider in terms of cleanliness and sanitation. This means that older people tend to look for cleanliness and sanitation as they avail the tourist attraction. According to [18], the importance of hospitable service and clean, well-run facilities, providing information about area attractions planned activities, providing opportunities for socialization and entertainment outlets are equally important. This suggests that the attractiveness of a tourist destination could be spoiled if the services and facilities that facilitate tourists' comforts would not met.

The Analysis of Variance to test differences in the factors in selecting Attraction as to Ambiance and Environment when grouped according to profile variables. The computed value of 0.876 for Gender, 0.220 for Age, 0.332 for Civil Status,

0.703 for Occupation, 0.335 for Monthly Income, and 0.063 for Preferred Type of Attraction was greater than > the 0.05 Alpha level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, hence, there is no significant difference on the factors in selecting Attraction as to Ambiance and Environment when grouped according to profile variables. This implies that ambiance and environment it is not significant when it comes to profile. According to [19], the perception of the environment is one of the above-mentioned elements and, in tourism, represents one of the factors in building the destination image. Thus, perception of the environment could be understood as perception of quality because the place itself, or the scenery, is what visitors want to see, which is a common theme identified in landscape planning literature when discussing this issue.

4 Conclusion

Overall, the findings of this research paper provide valuable insights into the profile of the respondents and the factors that influence their selection of attractions. The majority of the respondents were female and from the age group of 18 to 25 years old, with a mean age of 31 years old. In terms of civil status, most of the respondents were single, while in terms of occupation, the majority were from different occupations. The mean monthly income was 12,417.09, with most of the respondents earning 5,000 or below per month. Regarding the factors in selecting attractions, the respondents placed high importance on safety and security, management, cleanliness and sanitation, and ambiance and environment. These factors were ranked based on their perceived level of importance by the respondents, with the effectiveness of garbage and disposal segregation, quality of service, and the place being good for relaxation and stress-free surroundings being the top three factors. The computed overall weighted mean for each factor showed that they were all "very much considered" by the respondents. These findings can be useful for attraction managers and policymakers in understanding the preferences and priorities of their target audience. For instance, attraction managers can focus on enhancing safety measures, providing quality service, ensuring cleanliness and sanitation, and improving the ambiance and environment to attract more visitors. Policymakers can also use these findings to create policies and regulations that promote the development of safe, clean, and sustainable attractions that meet the needs of the public. This research sheds light on the profile of the respondents and the factors that influence their selection of attractions. The findings highlight the importance of safety, management, cleanliness and sanitation, and ambiance and environment in attracting visitors. The insights gained from this study can be useful for attraction managers and policymakers in creating attractive and sustainable destinations that cater to the needs of their target audience.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations have been identified. First and foremost, the tourist attraction management should prioritize the safety and security of their customers. This can be achieved by providing roving security guards who are visible and installing CCTV cameras to protect guests from harm. By doing so, tourists will feel safer and more secure during their visit, resulting in positive feedback and increased patronage. Secondly, the tourist attraction management should provide training and seminars to their employees on how to deal and serve customers properly. This will help them understand the importance of customer satisfaction and how it can contribute to the success of the business. Satisfied customers are more likely to return and recommend the attraction to others, resulting in increased revenue. Thirdly, the tourist attraction management should strictly implement the cleanliness of its surroundings. Maintaining a clean and hygienic environment is essential in attracting customers and creating a positive impression. This will help customers enjoy the place more and lead to repeat visits. Lastly, tourist attraction management should not only focus on the ambiance and environment but also offer activities that are good for individuals or groups. By providing activities, customers will have more options to choose from, leading to increased satisfaction and enjoyment. This can also encourage repeat visits and positive reviews. Implementing these recommendations can help tourist attraction management improve the overall customer experience, resulting in increased patronage, positive feedback, and higher revenue.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Gany, K. B. Visitors' (2017). Perception of Destination Attractiveness: The case of selected Kimberly Resort in the Department of Tourism and Event Management. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/222967476.pdf>
- [2] Jin, Qian, Hui Hu, and Philip Kavan. 2016. "Factors Influencing Perceived Crowding of Tourists and Sustainable Tourism Destination Management" *Sustainability* 8, no. 10: 976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8100976UNWTO> (2022). Introduction to tourism. Retrieved from <https://www.visitbritain.org/introduction-tourism>
- [3] Kankhuni, Z., & Ngwira C., (2018). What attracts tourists to a destination? Is it attractions? Retrieved from http://www.ajhtl.com/uploads/7/1/6/3/7163688/article_14_vol_7_1_2018.pdf
- [4] Rittichainuwat BN, Chakraborty G. (2012). Perceptions of importance and what safety is enough. *J Bus Res.* 2012 Jan;65(1):42-50. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.07.013. Epub 2011 Aug 30. PMID: 32287524; PMCID: PMC7124551.
- [5] Bekk, M., Spörrle, M., & Kruse, J. (2016). The benefits of similarity between tourist and destination personality. *Journal of Travel Research*, 55(8), 1008-1021. doi: 10.1177/0047287515606813
- [6] Bernini, C., Cracolici, M. F., & Nijkamp, P. (2017). Place-based attributes and spatial expenditure behavior in tourism. *Journal of Regional Science*, 57(2), 218-244. doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2014.09.016
- [7] Boavida-Portugal, I., Ferreira, C. C., & Rocha, J. (2017). Where to vacation? An agent-based approach to modelling tourist decision-making process. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 20(15), 1557-1574. doi: 10.1080/13683500.2015.1041880
- [8] Costa, V. (2022). Why solo Travel is Now the Number One Travel Trend Post Covid. Retrieved from <https://www.traveloffpath.com/why-solo-travel-is-now-the-number-one-travel-trend-post-covid/>
- [9] Goldstein, M. (2022). Why Do Women Like To Travel More Than Men? Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/michaelgoldstein/2022/12/08/why-do-women-like-to-travel-more-than-men/?sh=5441ec70339b>
- [10] Im, J. (2018). These are the Top 10 Travel Destinations on Earth, According to 100,000 Young People. Make It. Retrieved from <https://www.cnn.com/>
- [11] Jiao, X., Li, G., & Chen, J. (2020). Forecasting international tourism demand: A local spatiotemporal model. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 83(102937), 1-12. doi: 10.1016/j.annals.2020.102937
- [12] Kamruzzaman, Md., and Fariha, M., (2018). Effectiveness of Proper Health and Hygiene Practices: A Study on Ensuring Hygienic Environment in Bangladeshi Tourist Destinations
- [13] Karl, M. (2021) Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Germany TRAVEL DECISION-MAKING – Contributions by Marion Karl
- [14] Lauren (2022). How to travel for cheap? 8 ways to see the world with less money Retrieved from <https://www.worldpackers.com/articles/how-to-travel-for-cheap>
- [15] Li, Z., Shu, H., Tan, T., Huang, S., & Zha, J. (2020). Does the demographic structure affect outbound tourism demand? A panel smooth transition regression approach. *Journal of Travel Research*, 59(5), 893-908. doi: 10.1177/0047287519867141
- [16] Llego , M. (2021). Why Teachers should Travel?. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/why-teachers-should-travel>
- [17] Marinao, E. (2017), Determinants of Satisfaction with the Tourist Destination. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.70343
- [18] Morachat, C. (2013). A Study Of Destination Attractiveness Through Tourists Perspectives : A Focus On Chiang Mai, Thailand
- [19] Navratil, J., Picha, K., Rajchard, J., Navratilova, J. (2012). Impact of visit on visitors' perceptions of the environments of nature-based tourism sites.
- [20] RV and Playa (2016). Travel Statistics By Gender: 19 Facts Trends to Consider. Retrieved from <https://www.rvandplaya.com/travel-statistics-by-gender-facts-trends-to-know>
- [21] Santos, A. (2023). Human resource lens: perceived performances of ISO 9001:2015 certified service firms. *International Journal of Human Capital in Urban Management*, 8(2), 229-244. doi: 10.22034/IJHCUM.2023.02.06
- [22] Singleton, P. A. (2015). The theory of travel decision-making: a conceptual framework of active travel behavior.
- [23] Santos, A. R. . (2023). Critical success factors toward a safe city as perceived by selected medium enterprises in the province of Nueva Ecija: A crafted business development policy model. *Asian Development Policy Review*, 11(1), 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.55493/5008.v11i1.4750>